

Guidance

Animal-Based Indicators for Assessing Welfare Implications Related to Growth Rate in Broilers

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Emily M. Leishman¹ and Anja B. Riber¹

¹*Department of Animal and Veterinary Sciences, Aarhus University, Tjele, Denmark*

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1 Summary

Rapid growth rate in broiler chickens is increasingly scrutinised due to its association with several animal welfare concerns. This guidance synthesises current scientific evidence to identify animal-based indicators (ABIs) that are most informative, feasible on farm, and relevant for assessing welfare consequences related specifically to broiler growth rate based on scientific literature. Walking ability appears to be the strongest ABI for growth rate related welfare assessment. Evidence linking faster growth rates to impaired gait is consistent across breeds and production systems, and impaired walking ability is associated with consequences for pain, health, and behavioural expression. Indicators related to prolonged litter contact, such as footpad dermatitis and cleanliness, provide valuable complementary information but interpretation requires consideration of environmental factors like litter quality and stocking density. Assessment of leg straightness can be informative about the developmental and structural consequences of different growth rates. ABIs related to activity, such as standing vs. immobile, may provide further information when used alongside other mobility indicators. Other ABIs like mortality, activity level, qualitative behavioural assessment, positive and preferred behaviours, and integument measures (e.g., feather cover, skin lesions) can contribute additional context but are generally less specific to growth rate and can be influenced more strongly by management and environmental conditions. ABIs based on fear tests show limited and inconsistent associations with growth rate potentially due to confounds with broiler mobility and are not recommended in this context.

Overall, this guidance recommends prioritising ABIs related to mobility and activity when the goal is to assess broiler welfare specifically in the context of growth rate. These ABIs should be supported by other indicators of broiler welfare for a well-rounded assessment, and applied using standardised, reliable methods under comparable assessment conditions if comparing between flocks.

2 Introduction

The animal welfare implications of growth rate in poultry, particularly in broiler chickens, are increasingly scrutinised worldwide (Rayner et al., 2020), and have been the subject of several recent scientific literature reviews (Nicol et al., 2024; Riber & Wurtz, 2024). Intense genetic selection for rapid growth, high breast meat yield, and high feed efficiency has placed substantial developmental and metabolic pressure on modern broilers, resulting in a range of welfare consequences. The most commonly reported issues relate to impaired mobility and reduced capacity to perform motivated behaviours.

Despite these concerns, there is currently no specific limit on broiler growth rate in the EU legislation. However, growth rate regulation is a central component of many welfare labelling schemes and emerging policy initiatives including the European Chicken Commitment (ECC) and the US Better Chicken Commitment. For example, the ECC requires (among other things) that approved breeds comply with the RSPCA Better Broiler Welfare Assessment Protocol (RSPCA, 2017) which sets maximum average daily growth (ADG) rates of 60 g/d for indoor systems and 52 g/d for outdoor systems.

In addition, some national welfare labels stipulate stricter growth rate limits. These include the French Label Rouge program (26 g/d) and the Dutch Beter Leven program (45 g/d). As a result of this variation, there is no universally accepted definition of a “slower-growing” broiler. In practice, slower-growing broilers have been classified as having an average growth rate of less than 50 g/d whereas fast-growing broilers exceed this threshold (Rayner et al., 2020).

The purpose of this guidance is to provide suggestions for animal-based indicators (ABIs) that could be incorporated into an on-farm welfare assessment of broilers, with a special focus on welfare outcomes associated with growth rate based on scientific literature.

3 Animal-Based Indicators Related to Growth Rate

Animal-based indicators (ABIs) refer to a direct or indirect response of an animal or an effect on an animal used to assess its welfare, in contrast to evaluations of resource provision or management processes (resource- or management-based indicators; RBIs or MBIs) (Butterworth, 2009; EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2020). Since animal welfare is a characteristic of the individual animal rather than the production system, ABIs are generally considered more valid indicators of welfare status than RBMs (Butterworth, 2009).

This section focuses on ABIs that are commonly studied in relation to broiler growth rate on-farm. Potential ABIs were identified through a search of the scientific literature using keywords such as “broiler chicken”, “growth rate”, and “welfare” and through inspection of broiler welfare assessment protocols. ABIs that require assessment at slaughter, laboratory analysis, or veterinary post-mortem assessment are therefore not included. ABIs lacking scientific evidence for a relationship specifically with broiler growth rate were also not included. ABIs are roughly presented in order of perceived relevance for assessment of broiler welfare relative to growth rate based on the amount and consistency of scientific evidence. For each ABI, the section provides: (1) a brief description of the ABI, (2) a summary of the scientific evidence describing its relationship with growth rate, (3) an overview of methods typically used to record the ABI, and (4) a brief conclusion on the ABIs suitability and relevance for on-farm welfare assessment in the context of growth rate. The term “breed” is used throughout this document to refer to a commercially defined population of broiler chickens (e.g., Ross 308, Cobb 700, Hubbard JA) sharing a similar genetic background as a result of systematic selective breeding and crossbreeding programs, and characterised by consistent, heritable differences in growth rate.

Walking Ability

ABI description

Walking ability refers to the broiler’s capacity to engage in smooth, fluid locomotion (RSPCA, 2017). It is a frequently used ABI in studies examining the relationship between broiler welfare and growth rate (Nicol et al., 2024) and is a mandatory ABI in several welfare assessment schemes, including the RSPCA’s Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol (RSPCA, 2017) and WelfareQuality® (2009). Difficulty walking is widely recognised as a major welfare concern in broiler chickens and has been described as a “flagship” indicator of broader welfare compromise (Dawkins, 2024).

Broilers with impaired walking ability may experience pain (Caplen et al., 2013; Caplen et al., 2014) and have a reduced ability to perform essential and motivated behaviours such as walking, foraging, perching, and comfort behaviours (Abeyesinghe et al., 2021; Riber et al., 2021; Weeks et al., 2000). In addition to reflecting physical capacity, walking ability may also provide insight into the bird’s motivation to move, thereby capturing elements relevant to positive welfare (Abeyesinghe et al., 2021; Dawkins, 2024).

Relationship with growth rate

Differences in walking ability between broiler breeds with varying growth rates are consistently reported in the literature. Rasmussen et al. (2024) found that at the same weight (approximately 2 kg) organic broilers (Ranger Gold; 49-55 days at assessment) displayed better walking ability than conventional broilers (Ross 308; 31-33 days at assessment). Similarly, Averós et al. (2022) reported better walking ability in medium-growing flocks (avg. 48 days at assessment; Hubbard JA x Ross 308; 11.7 broilers/m³) compared to fast-growing flocks (avg. 32 days at assessment; Ross 308/Cobb 500/Both; 16.5 broilers/m³) just prior to slaughter. Rayner et al. (2020) reported that fewer slower-growing broilers (0.5 – 3.5%, 30 and 34 g/d) showed evidence of poor walking ability (gait score of ≥ 3 on Bristol scale, which indicates a gait that impacts bird ability to manoeuvre), compared fast-growing broilers (16.3%) when assessed two days before slaughter. This is also seen, in birds of the same genetics (Cobb 700) that are fed different diets to achieve varying growth rates slow (<50 g/d), medium (50-60 g/d), or fast (>60 g/d), as found by Zhou et al. (2024). They found that the slower-growing broilers had significantly better walking ability compared to medium and fast-growing broilers when assessed at the same bodyweight, and there was no difference between the medium and fast-growing broilers. Guinebretière et al. (2024) reported a significantly higher percentage of birds with no walking defects in Redbro (49 g/d), Rustic Gold (48 g/d), Ranger Classic (47 g/d), JA 787 (46 g/d), and JA 757 (47 g/d) breeds (87.7 – 99.1% without defect) compared to Ross 308 (61 g/d, 54.4% without defect) when assessed at the same body weight. Santos et al. (2022) showed that the slowest growing birds had a greater ability and/or willingness to remain standing, which is associated with improved welfare. Taken together, these findings indicate a worsening of walking ability with increasing growth rate. Although it should be acknowledged that walking ability can be linked to factors other than growth rate, including skeletal and muscular development, nutrition, housing conditions, activity level, health status, and environmental conditions.

Overview of recording methods

Walking ability can be assessed on farm using visual gait scoring systems (i.e., Bristol Scale; (Kestin et al., 1992)) or proxy measures such as the latency-to-lie test (Wurtz et al., 2025).

Visual gait scoring using the Bristol scale (Kestin et al., 1992) is widely applied in welfare assessment protocols. For example, under the RSPCA Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol, one or more assessors observe birds walking for at least 10 paces and assign a score from 0 to 5, where 0 represents smooth, fluid locomotion and 5 indicates the bird is incapable of sustained walking. Gait scores of 4-5 are typically considered unacceptable and result in culling (Dixon, 2020; Kapell et al., 2025), although birds scoring 1-3 may still experience compromised welfare due to instability or impaired movement (Caplen et al., 2012; Riber et al., 2021; Tahamtani et al., 2021; Weeks et al., 1998).

The latency-to-lie test provides an alternative, quantitative measure of walking ability. The original protocol involved placing birds in a box with shallow water and recording the time until the bird sits. This has been adapted for on-farm use by substituting water with litter-filled

boxes. Wurtz et al. (2025) demonstrated that this modified approach can be conducted reliably, improving feasibility for on-farm assessments. Since the ABI is measured quantitatively as time, this method is less subjective and likely more consistent across observers.

Suitability for welfare assessment

Walking ability is a highly relevant and feasible ABI for assessing welfare consequences associated with growth rate in broilers on farm. Impaired walking or the inability to walk can be painful, restricts the ability to perform necessary behaviours such as feeding and drinking and other motivated behaviours like foraging and perching, and reduces opportunities for positive experiences. It is worth noting, as with all ABIs measured using a visual scale with multiple observers, care should be taken to ensure consistency. Overall, walking ability is a meaningful indicator for evaluating welfare consequences of growth rate.

Activity Level

ABI description

Activity level often refers to the extent and pattern of voluntary movement displayed by broiler chickens, including standing, walking, and other forms of locomotion. Detailed behavioural observations can be impractical on-farm; however, advances in precision poultry farming and digital technologies (e.g., automated tracking systems) are making general activity assessment more feasible (Dawkins, 2024). Dawkins (2024) identified active walking (defined as walking continuously with regular strides for a specified time) as a “flagship” indicator of broiler welfare since this voluntary active movement indicates physical ability and health, as well as the motivation to move. Prolonged inactivity may indicate impaired walking ability or discomfort, which is associated with compromised welfare.

Relationship with growth rate

Evidence suggests that activity level differs between broiler breeds with varying growth rates, with fast-growing birds generally displaying less voluntary movement. Abeyesinghe et al. (2021) reported that fast-growing broilers (approx. 66 g/d) showed a higher frequency of side-lying inactive behaviour at day 29 compared to two slower-growing broilers breeds (approx. 42 – 48 g/d). Slower-growing birds also spend more time standing inactive, indicating they stood more frequently and for longer durations than fast-growing broilers at the same age. This might be attributed to slower-growing broilers experiencing less pain, discomfort, or instability with standing compared to fast-growing broilers. Zhou et al. (2024) reported a higher “activity index” quantified as the number of moving animals obtained from image analysis (Yang et al., 2020) in slower-growing broilers (<50 g/d) compared to fast-growing broilers (>60 g/d) regardless of the bodyweight at assessment (assessed at 1, 2, and 3 kg). The activity index of medium growing broilers (50-60 g/d) was intermediate and not significantly different from either group. Additionally, Malchow et al. (2019) reported less locomotor activity throughout the rearing period of fast-growing male Ross 308 broilers compared to slower-growing male Lohmann Dual Purpose broilers and male Lohmann Brown Plus broilers. Guinebrière et al. (2024) also found that the percentage of broilers standing was 2.3 – 3.1 times lower in the fastest-growing Ross 308 compared to Redbro, Ranger Classic, JA 787, and JA 575 breeds

when assessed at the same body weight. Taken together, these studies indicate that increasing growth rate is generally associated with reduced activity which could be used to indicate physical ability and/or behavioural motivation to move.

Overview of recording methods

Activity level is not typically included in on-farm welfare assessment protocols due to the traditional reliance on behavioural observations which are not always feasible on-farm. Advances in digital technologies may eventually provide feasible on-farm recording methods that could be incorporated into welfare assessment protocols.

Some protocols like the Transect Walk (Marchewka et al., 2013) include recording all occurrences of immobile birds (no attempt to move, even after slight encouragement) in strategically chosen areas of the barn. Using the same method, it may also be possible to record the number of birds standing or actively moving in a transect as a more feasible option, or record walking ability due to the connection between immobility and walking ability.

Suitability for welfare assessment

In the future, activity level has a lot of potential as an ABI to assess the welfare of broilers relative to growth rate since it can act as a “flagship” due to its connection with physical capability and behavioural motivation. It may be possible to assess a proxy for activity level by observing the number of immobile or standing birds during welfare assessments, but this ABI should only be considered alongside other indicators to assess welfare consequences of growth rate on health and mobility. Like other behavioural time budget ABIs, there are also other limitations to its use and interpretation such as time of day and age-related influences and setting threshold values for an acceptable level of activity, that should be considered before being applied.

Mortality

ABI description

Mortality is a commonly used outcome-based measure, that refers to the number of animals found dead in a flock (WelfareQuality®, 2009). In some definitions, mortality also includes the number of culled animals (Rayner et al., 2020). It is the most frequently reported welfare indicator in studies comparing fast- and slower-growing broiler chickens (Nicol et al., 2024). Alongside overall mortality, some authors have proposed inclusion of more specific indicators, e.g., culls due to lameness (Rayner et al., 2020) or deaths associated with cardiovascular conditions (e.g., ascites, sudden death syndrome), as ABIs related to growth rate (EFSA, 2010).

Relationship with growth rate

There is evidence that slower-growing broilers experience lower mortality, potentially due to reduced susceptibility to life-threatening metabolic and cardiovascular disorders or conditions that lead to culling (i.e., severe lameness). Rayner et al. (2020) reported higher 7-day ($2.08 \pm 0.29\%$) and total mortality ($6.23 \pm 0.62\%$) in a fast-growing broiler breed (63 g/d ; 34 kg/m^3) compared to two slower growing breeds (7d: $0.76 - 1.27\%$; total: $2.10 - 3.20\%$; $30-34 \text{ g/d}$; $30-34 \text{ kg/m}^3$). Similarly, Dixon et al. (2020) observed higher overall mortality (found dead +

culls) in two out of three studied fast-growing breeds (breeds anonymised; Breed A: $0.11 \pm 0.01\%$; Breed B: $0.11 \pm 0.02\%$) compared to what they defined as a slow-growing breed (Hubbard JA575; $0.05 \pm 0.01\%$; 46 g/d) and the third fast-growing breed ($0.07 \pm 0.02\%$).

More recent work by Slegers et al. (2024) reported lower mortality in breeds that they defined as slower- (1.9% , 95% CI [1.8, 2.0], 56 day median slaughter age, mainly Hubbard and Ross Ranger flocks) and medium- growing (2.0% , 95% CI [1.9, 2.1], 50 day median slaughter age, mainly Hubbard flocks) compared to fast-growing breeds (3.2% , 95% CI [3.0, 3.4], 42 day median slaughter age, mainly Ross 308 flocks), with the lowest mortality observed in the slower-growing breeds. However, growth rates and specific breeds were not reported. In contrast, Torrey et al. (2021) found no relationship between breed category (slow, medium, fast, conventional) and overall mortality, but they found differences between categories in the odds of being culled. Birds from slow-growing breeds had lower odds of being culled than all other categories (odds ratio: 0.134 – 0.272). Contrary to other studies, slow-growing birds had the highest percentage of birds found dead ($2.22 \pm 0.33\%$) compared to conventional ($1.99 \pm 0.55\%$), fast-growing ($1.65 \pm 0.27\%$), and medium-growing ($1.47 \pm 0.31\%$) breeds. These findings highlight that faster growth rates are usually associated with higher mortality rates and culling, however, there are some inconsistencies in the literature which may be due to additional factors like housing and management.

Overview of recording methods

Mortality assessment typically include recording the number of birds found dead, the number of birds culled (including reason for culling), and mortality rate at different ages (EFSA, 2010). Where feasible, post-mortem examination can provide further information such as the prevalence of ascites or sudden death syndrome, which may improve the interpretation of mortality data in relation to growth rate.

Suitability for welfare assessment

Mortality alone is a limited ABI for welfare assessment because it is retrospective and often recorded too late for practical intervention for the affected individual or current flock. Nevertheless, it can provide valuable complementary information for later flocks when used alongside other ABIs and may function as an “iceberg indicator” of compromised welfare. While high mortality rates are likely indicative of conditions adversely affecting welfare, the relationship between mortality and growth rate can be difficult to discern from the literature due to the wide variety of housing and management conditions being compared. Mortality should therefore be used only in combination with other ABIs when assessing welfare consequences of broiler growth rate.

Leg straightness

ABI description

Leg straightness refers to the alignment of the legs and reflects aspects of normal skeletal development in broiler chickens. Leg disorders (e.g., bacterial chondronecrosis with osteomyelitis, tibial dyschondroplasia, valgus varus deformity) are highly prevalent welfare

problems in broilers. While many leg disorders require advanced imaging or post-mortem examination and are therefore not readily assessed on-farm, some angular deformities, particularly valgus varus deformity (VVD), can be recorded during typical welfare assessment.

Valgus varus deformity (VVD) is a developmental condition where the legs exhibit outward (valgus) or inward (varus) angulation. Birds affected by VVD may experience impaired standing and locomotion ability and are also at increased risk of secondary leg problems like slipped tendons or fractures (Bradshaw et al., 2002; Julian, 1984; van den Brand et al., 2022). Consequently, leg straightness is included as an ABI in welfare assessments like the RSPCA Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol (2017).

Relationship with growth rate

The main hypothesized cause of VVD is rapid weight gain during development and inadequate nutrition that results in the twisting of the leg bones. Shim et al. (2012) found more incidences of valgus deformities in broilers growing 45 g/d (27.7 – 29.4%) compared to broilers growing 33 g/d (18.9 – 20.0%).

Earlier studies have demonstrated that reducing growth rate through nutritional interventions, such as lowering dietary energy content, can reduce the incidence of VVD (Classen & Riddell, 1989; Leterrier et al., 1998). Together, these findings indicate that VVD and leg straightness are influenced by growth rate and can be used to indicate compromised bone development.

Overview of recording methods

On-farm assessment of leg straightness is included in the RSPCA Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol (RSPCA, 2017), conducted using the scoring system of Dawkins et al. (2004). This approach involves visual assessment to record the presence or absence of inward angled legs, outward angled legs, twisted metatarsus, and/or rotated tibia. In this protocol, scoring requires brief handling and inversion followed by manual inspection of the legs.

Suitability for welfare assessment

Assessment of leg straightness can provide useful information on welfare consequences related to growth rate, particularly with respect to normal skeletal development and structural integrity of the broiler.

Contact Dermatitis

ABI description

Contact dermatitis, typically in the form of hock burn and footpad dermatitis, is a common ABI for assessing broiler welfare related to growth rate (Nicol et al., 2024). This ABI assesses the presence and severity of visible lesions on the footpads and hocks, these lesions are areas of ulcerative, infected and/or necrotic tissue. There is evidence that these lesions can be painful in turkeys (Sinclair et al., 2015; Weber Wyneken et al., 2015) and therefore it is assumed that welfare is reduced with increasing prevalence and severity of these lesions.

Contact dermatitis is closely linked to environmental conditions, such as litter quality and stocking density (reviewed in Mayne, 2005; Shepherd & Fairchild, 2010), and some studies report an association between dermatitis and walking ability (De Jong et al., 2014; Haslam et al., 2007; Kittelsen et al., 2024). Therefore, this ABI is frequently incorporated into broiler welfare assessments. Broilers with reduced mobility are thought to be at greater risk of developing contact dermatitis due to increased contact with the litter, although this can vary considerably depending on environmental factors like litter quality and stocking density.

Relationship with growth rate

Evidence suggests that fast-growing broilers generally exhibit higher levels of contact dermatitis, although stocking density can influence the results. Rayner et al. (2020) reported greater prevalence of hock burn in fast-growing broilers (63 g/d; 34 kg/m² compared to slower-growing broilers (30-34 g/d) reared at a lower stocking density (30 kg/m²). However, when the slower-growing breed was kept at the same stocking density as the fast-growing birds (34 kg/m³), levels of hock burn were more alike (18.14 vs. 26.70% affected), indicating that hock burn may be more reflective of environmental conditions than growth rate alone. Likewise, Weimer et al. (2020) found that hock burn was higher in slow-growing broilers (breed not specified, 44 g/d) compared to fast-growing broilers (breed not specified, 67 g/d) at 29 kg/m² when assessed just before slaughter, however there was no difference when both breeds were kept at 37 kg/m². Van der Eijk (2023) similarly reported less hock burn in slower-growing broilers (Ranger Classic) when birds were compared to fast-growing broilers (Ross 308) at the same body weight (2.3 kg). Dixon (2020) reported that slow-growing broilers (JA 575) had better hock burn scores than the three studied fast-growing breeds (Ross 308, Cobb 500, Hubbard Flex). However, Guinebretière et al. (2024) found no difference between breeds varying in growth rate from 42 – 61 g/d (Ross 308, Redbro, Rustic Gold, Ranger Classic, JA 787, JA 757), nor an interaction between breed and stocking density (37 vs. 29 kg/m²).

Footpad dermatitis appears to show a more consistent association with growth rate. It is consistently demonstrated that fast-growing broilers have a higher prevalence and severity of footpad dermatitis (Abeyesinghe et al., 2021; Bokkers & Koene, 2003; Bokkers & Koene, 2004; Castellini et al., 2016). With regards to stocking density, Rayner et al. (2020) observed higher levels of footpad dermatitis in fast-growing broilers kept at 34 kg/m² compared to a slow-growing breed kept at both 30 and 34 kg/m² and another slow-growing breed kept at 30 kg/m². Van der Eijk (2023) demonstrated that faster-growing broilers developed more footpad dermatitis at 24 and 30 kg/m² compared to 42 kg/m², and consistently more than slow-growing broilers across all stocking densities examined (24-42 kg/m²). Malchow et al. (2019) reported that fast-growing male Ross 308 broilers showed worse footpad health compared to slower-growing male Lohmann Dual Purpose chickens and male Lohmann Brown Plus chickens at the end of the rearing period. Abeyesinghe et al. (2021) reported a higher pen mean percentage of footpad dermatitis in one breed of fast-growing broilers (66 g/d, 100%) compared to two slower-growing breeds (46 g/d, 49 g/d, 0% respectively) when assessed at the same weight. In the study of Zhou et al. (2024), they found that footpad dermatitis was numerically higher in what they defined as fast- (>60 g/d, average score 0.23) and medium-growing broilers (50-

60 g/d, average score 0.22) compared to slower-growing broilers (<50 g/d, average score 0.13), however, this difference was not statistically significant. Guinebrière et al. (2024) reported an interaction between stocking density and breed on footpad dermatitis prevalence. In high density pens (37 kg/m²), footpad dermatitis prevalence was highest in Ross 308 (61 g/d, 21.2% affected), Redbro (49 g/d, 15.5% affected), and JA 787 (46 g/d, 18.9% affected) than Rustic Gold (48 g/d, 6.1% affected), Ranger Classic (47 g/d, 7.3% affected), and JA 757 (42 g/d, 6.5% affected). No differences between strains were found at low density (29 kg/m²). These findings suggest that footpad dermatitis may be a more informative ABI than hock burn for detecting welfare consequences associated with growth rate.

Overview of recording methods

Contact dermatitis is typically assessed on-farm or at slaughter through visual inspection of the footpads and hocks. As described in the WelfareQuality® protocol (WelfareQuality®, 2009), footpads and hocks can be assigned a score between 0 (no lesions) and 4 (severe lesions) where higher scores are assumed to correspond with worse welfare.

Suitability for welfare assessment

Contact dermatitis, particularly footpad dermatitis, is a recommended ABI for assessing welfare outcomes related to broiler growth rate. Given its association with mobility and litter quality, it provides complementary information to direct assessments of walking ability. However, careful interpretation is required due to the strong influence of environmental factors.

Positive and Preferred Behaviours

ABI definition

Positive behaviour refers to behaviours thought to reflect positive emotional states and/or the expression of motivated natural behaviours (Lawrence et al., 2019; Rault et al., 2025). A higher frequency or longer duration of positive behaviours is thought to indicate better welfare. In broiler chickens, some positive behaviours commonly assessed on-farm include play-related behaviours (e.g., worm running, sparring, frolicking), locomotor behaviours (e.g., running, jumping, wing flapping) and exploratory or comfort behaviours (e.g., ground scratching, leg/wing stretching) (Rayner et al., 2020). Preferred behaviours can include those that broiler chickens may be motivated to perform through natural selection and evolution (i.e., perching, foraging, roosting) and an inability to perform these behaviours results in frustration (Riber & Wurtz, 2024).

ABIs related to positive and preferred behaviours are frequently recorded in broiler welfare assessments since these behaviours often involve sustained or sudden bursts of activity. Expression of such behaviours may therefore be constrained in fast-growing broilers due to reduced mobility, limited cardiovascular capacity, or less space, linking positive behaviour not only to emotional state but also to physical ability (Riber & Wurtz, 2024).

Relationship with growth rate

Several studies have compared the expression of positive behaviours between broiler breeds with different growth rates due to the association with positive emotions and capacity to engage

in energetically demanding behaviours. Rayner et al. (2020) found that positive behaviour rates depended on whether the birds were observed in disturbed (open areas created by an observer walking through the flock) or undisturbed conditions. In disturbed patches, significantly more play behaviour (3.2-4.1x higher odds) was observed in slower-growing broilers (45-49 g/d; 30 or 34 kg/m³) than fast-growing broilers (63 g/d; 34 kg/m³), regardless of stocking density. Similarly, Averós et al. (2022) reported more frequent play fighting, wing flapping, and running in what they defined as medium-growing flocks (Hubbard JA x Ross 308; 48 days at assessment) compared to fast-growing flocks (Ross 308/Cobb 500/Mix; 32 days at measurement) at the end of the production cycle. These findings suggest that fast growth may reduce the expression of high-energy play behaviours.

However, this pattern was not observed by Rasmussen et al. (2024) who found that organic broilers (Ranger Gold; 21 kg/m², 48-55 days at assessment) displayed less play behaviour in disturbed (open) patches compared to conventional broilers (Ross 308, 40 kg/m², 31-33 days at assessment). The authors suggest that this finding might reflect compensatory behaviour in the fast-growing conventional broilers who take advantage of the space-generating effect of disturbance to perform high-energy behaviours, whereas slower-growing broilers have more space and therefore are not as stimulated to play in the new open spaces. It may also reflect age related differences in the likelihood to engage in certain behaviours related to play.

In addition to play and locomotor behaviours, some motivated natural behaviours associated with exploration and comfort differ by growth rate. Perching is a well-studied motivated behaviour in broilers. Abeyesinghe et al. (2021) reported that slower-growing breeds perched more frequently than a fast-growing breed at day 29, but they also weighed less. Similarly, the number of bales having one or more birds on top expressed as a percentage of the total number of bales in the house has been used as a positive welfare indicator (Rayner et al., 2020). Rayner et al. (2020) found that fast-growing (63 g/d) birds did not spend any time (0 ± 0.0 % bales occupied) on the bales across any stage of production, whereas slower-growing (30-34 g/d) breeds occupied 84-93% of the bales up until 3 days before processing.

Overview of recording methods

Positive and preferred behaviours are typically recorded through direct behavioural observations. Observations may be conducted after the birds are disturbed during the transect method (Marchewka et al., 2015; Marchewka et al., 2013) with behaviours of interest recorded as frequencies, durations, or presence/absence within a defined observation period. It may be more feasible on farm to record proxies such as perch or enrichment use, or range use in the case of outdoor systems. However, in this case one must take into account the availability, type, and distribution within the house of the enrichment items to avoid misinterpretation.

Suitability for welfare assessment

Assessment of positive behaviours can provide valuable insight into emotional state and physical ability. However, suitability of these ABIs depends on the conditions under which the data are collected and production stage. Conflicting findings across a limited number of studies, particularly regarding play behaviour, suggest that the methods used for data collection can

influence the test outcome and may cause difficulty interpreting the effect of growth rate. Consequently, while positive behaviour measures can contribute meaningfully to welfare assessment, they should be interpreted cautiously alongside other ABIs.

Cleanliness

ABI description

Cleanliness, typically assessed by the degree of soiling of the breast plumage, is an ABI that reflects litter quality and the amount of time birds spend sitting. Poor cleanliness may be associated with discomfort, increased risk of contact dermatitis, and impaired thermoregulatory ability (WelfareQuality®, 2009).

Relationship with growth rate

Cleanliness appears to show a relatively consistent association with growth rate, although this relationship is influenced by environmental context. Van der Eijk (2023) found that slower-growing broilers were cleaner at 2.3 kg compared to fast-growing broilers, suggesting that fast growth rates may be associated with increased litter contact. Malchow et al. (2019) found that fast-growing male Ross 308 broilers were dirtier than slower-growing male Lohmann Dual Purpose chickens and male Lohmann Brown Plus chickens at the end of the rearing period. Zhou et al. (2024) further demonstrated interactions between growth and stocking density by manipulating the dietary energy content of Cobb 700 broilers to achieve slower (<50 g/d), medium (50-60 g/d), and fast (>60 g/d) growth rates, and reared the birds at either 30 or 40 kg/m³. They found that at the high stocking density, the plumage became dirtier when growth rate increased from slower to medium, whereas at the low stocking density plumage became dirtier when growth rate increased from medium to fast. This highlights that fast-growing broilers typically have dirtier plumage, but this effect can depend on the stocking density and environmental conditions.

Overview of recording methods

In some assessment schemes, cleanliness is scored by inspecting the plumage of the breast area and scoring between 0 (completely clean) and 3 (very dirty) (WelfareQuality®, 2009). This scheme is also used in the RSCPA BBWAP, but WelfareQuality® scores 2 and 3 are combined (RSPCA, 2017).

Suitability for welfare assessment

Cleanliness can provide useful information on welfare consequences of broiler growth rate but can be influenced by environmental factors such as stocking density, litter quality, and enrichment provision. Moreover, breast cleanliness assessment may be challenging in breeds with poorly feathered breasts making comparisons between breeds difficult. Consequently, cleanliness is best interpreted alongside other ABIs for insight into welfare consequences of growth rate.

Qualitative Behaviour Assessment (QBA)

ABI description

Qualitative Behaviour Assessment (QBA) is an ABI that aims to capture the overall behavioural expression and affective state of animals, rather than focusing on discrete behaviours (Czycholl et al., 2025). QBA is based on the premise that observers can interpret multiple aspects of animal posture, movement, and interaction into qualitative descriptors that reflect how animals are experiencing their environment (e.g., calm, tense, energetic, fearful). As such, in the case of broiler welfare assessment, QBA aims to provide a holistic assessment of emotional expression at the flock level.

Relationship with growth rate

Evidence linking QBA outcomes specifically to broiler growth rate is limited, but some studies suggest that growth rate and production stage may influence behavioural expression. Rayner et al. (2020) reported that fast-growing broilers (63 g/d; 34 kg/m³) were scored as more 'flat' and 'stressed' compared to slower-growing broilers (45-49 g/d, 30-34 kg/m²). This difference was also observed when slower-growing birds were housed at the same stocking density as the fast-growing birds, suggesting that growth rate may contribute to QBA outcomes independent of stocking density.

In addition, Rayner et al. (2020) found that QBA scores in fast-growing birds were influenced by production stage. Specifically, behavioural expression shifted over time from descriptors associated with more positive states (e.g., happy, active) toward descriptors associated with more negative affect (e.g., flat, stressed) as birds approached the end of the production cycle. This pattern was less pronounced in slower-growing birds.

Differences in QBA outcomes have also been reported between production systems that typically use breeds with differing growth rates. Rasmussen et al. (2024) found that organic broilers were described as more active, energetic, positively occupied, happy, and agitated than conventional broilers when assessed near the end of production. However, they found that the outcome of the test was influenced by which observer was conducting the test, indicating it should be used cautiously in practice and reliability between observers should be verified (Rasmussen et al., 2024).

Overall, while some evidence suggests that fast growth rates may be associated with more negatively valenced qualitative behavioural expressions, particularly near the end of production, the relationship between growth rate and QBA is not yet well established and can be influenced by factors such as production stage, housing system, and observer.

Overview of recording methods

QBA involves scoring a predefined list of qualitative descriptors that characterise the behavioural expression of a flock using a visual analogue scale. In the WelfareQuality (2009) protocol, a fixed list of descriptors is used to promote standardization across observers. These descriptors include: active, relaxed, helpless, comfortable, calm, content, tense, inquisitive,

friendly, positively occupied, scared, drowsy, fearful, agitated, confident, depressed, unsure, energetic, frustrated, bored, playful, nervous, and distressed.

Observers assess the flock from up to 8 observation points within the house, ensuring that different areas are covered. Birds are observed for a total duration of up to 20 minutes, with time per observation point adjusted according to the number of points used (e.g., 8 observation points = 2.5 min max. per point; 4 observation points = 5 min max. per point). Importantly, scoring of the descriptors is performed only after all observations are completed, based on the observer's overall impression of flock behaviour.

Suitability for welfare assessment

QBA can be used to indicate the overall affective state and behavioural expression of broiler flocks and some evidence suggests differences between fast- and slower-growing broilers. Therefore, QBA may be a suitable ABI for assessing welfare consequences relative to growth rate since growth rate has been shown to affect activity level and time spent on positive behaviours. As such, QBA could be used as a supplementary ABI to gain insight into overall behavioural expression if it is not feasible to collect targeted behavioural ABIs like activity level or positive and preferred behaviours. It should be noted that the outcome of the QBA can vary with observer and production stage and this should be accounted for when interpreting results.

Skin Lesions

ABI description

Skin lesion refers to wounds (non-linear lesion) and scratches (linear lesion) on the body of the bird (Allain et al., 2009; van der Eijk et al., 2023; WelfareQuality®, 2009). These lesions can be a result of abrasions from the environment or from interactions with other birds. Skin lesions can reduce welfare through damage to the skin and increasing the likelihood of secondary infections. Therefore, similar to other ABIs related to physical damage, it is assumed that an increased number and/or severity of lesions is associated with worse welfare.

Relationship with growth rate

Differences in skin injury prevalence have also been reported in relation to growth rate. van der Eijk (2023) found that slower-growing broilers had fewer skin lesions compared to fast-growing broilers at 2.0 and 2.3 kg regardless of stocking density (24 – 42 kg/m²). In addition, Averós et al. (2022) reported a higher prevalence of tail-wounded birds (presumably from injurious pecking) in fast-growing flocks compared to medium-growing flocks. However, it should be noted that fast-growing flocks had an average stocking density of 16.5 broilers/m² whereas slow-growing flocks had an average density of 11.7 m². In a comparison of slower-growing breeds (Ranger Classic, Ranger Gold, Rowan Ranger, Rambler Ranger), Louton et al. (2019) found that the slowest growing breed, Rambler Ranger, showed the lowest prevalence of skin scratches at day 44 regardless of whether birds had access to a winter garden (indoor stocking density 29 kg/m²) or not (25 kg/m²). These findings may reflect increased susceptibility to integument damage in fast-growing birds. However, it should be noted that the prevalence of scratches can also be influenced by environmental complexity. In the

assessment of the four different slower-growing breeds, Louton et al. (2019) found that across breeds more scratches were found in groups with access to a winter garden who are presumed to be more active.

Overview of recording methods

Skin lesions are typically assigned a score 0 (no scratches or wounds), 1 (single scratch or small wound $\leq 0.5 \text{ cm}^2$), or 2 (multiple scratches and/or large wounds $> 0.5 \text{ cm}^2$) (van der Eijk et al., 2023; WelfareQuality®, 2009).

Suitability for welfare assessment

Skin lesions assessed on farm can provide useful information regarding injuries and potential discomfort or the occurrence of injurious behaviours. Some evidence suggests that faster-growing broilers may be more susceptible to skin lesions, however, there is also evidence for a relationship between scratches and activity level. Therefore, skin lesions should be interpreted cautiously and in combination with other ABIs when considering differences between broiler breeds with different activity levels. With respect to consequences of growth rate, skin lesions should not be assessed at slaughter since lesions can occur during catching or transport which are not directly related to growth rate.

Feather Cover

ABI description

Feather cover refers to the quantity and distribution of feathers on the bird. Feather cover is influenced by age and genetics, and changes to feather cover during production may be associated with friction against the litter, equipment, or interactions with other birds, depending on the body location affected (Bilčík & Keeling, 1999). Feathers play a key role in protecting the skin from damage, communication, and thermoregulation (Mota-Rojas et al., 2021; Terrill & Shultz, 2023) and therefore it is assumed that reduced feather cover is associated with poorer welfare.

Relationship with growth rate

Evidence suggests that feather cover differs between broiler breeds with different growth rates. Averós et al. (2022) reported a higher percentage of featherless birds in what they define as fast-growing (Ross 308/Cobb 500/Mix; 32 days at assessment) flocks compared to medium-growing flocks (Hubbard JA x Ross 308, 48 days at assessment). Zhou et al. (2024) found that fast-growing broilers ($> 60 \text{ g/d}$) had the lowest belly feather coverage (approximately 3% more exposed skin area), compared to slower ($< 50 \text{ g/d}$) and medium growing ($50\text{-}60 \text{ g/d}$) Cobb 700 broilers when assessed at the same body weight. Guinebretière et al. (2024) reported 0% of Ross 308 broilers having full plumage coverage (score 0) on the body, back, and wings (breast not assessed) compared to Redbro (22.6% fully covered), Rustic Gold (27.4% fully covered), Ranger Classic (29.6% fully covered), JA 787 (31.1% fully covered), and JA 757 (67.9% fully covered). These findings suggest that rapid growth may compromise feather coverage.

Overview of recording methods

Feather cover is scored in the RSCPA BBWAP (RSPCA, 2017) using the method of Dawkins et al. (2004) which scores feather cover in 0.5 increments from 0 (feather cover full and even over body and wings) to 2 (body bare of feathers and wings are patchy).

Suitability for welfare assessment

Adequate feather cover is important for poultry welfare and differences in feather cover have been demonstrated between breeds with different growth rates. However, feather cover assessment can be influenced by the age of assessment and genetic or sex related differences in feathering rates as well as other confounding factors like nutrition and the environment. As such, feather cover assessment may not be the most informative ABI when assessing welfare consequences of growth rate due to the numerous factors assessing feathering which are difficult to control for in practice.

Fear Response

ABI description

Fear is considered a negative affective state, and excessive fearfulness is associated with stress, increased risk of injury, and overall compromised welfare (Rushen et al., 1999). Behavioural assessments of fearfulness are therefore commonly incorporated into welfare assessment protocols such as WelfareQuality® (2009).

Fearfulness in broilers is typically assessed using behavioural tests that measure avoidance of novel or potentially threatening stimuli, including unfamiliar objects (e.g., novel object test) or humans (e.g., avoidance distance test, touch test). These tests aim to infer a bird's emotional response based on proximity, approach/avoidance behaviour, or latency to interact with the stimuli.

Relationship with growth rate

Several studies have examined differences in fear responses relative to broiler growth rate, although results are inconsistent. Averós et al. (2022) reported a higher proportion of fast-growing broilers (Ross 308/Cobb 500/Mixed flocks) remained close to an observer during avoidance tests, which could be interpreted as lower fearfulness compared to what they define as medium-growing broilers (Hubbard JA x Ross 308). However, the authors suggested that this apparent reduction in fear response may be confounded by the higher stocking densities of the fast-growing flocks, which likely restricts the birds' ability to move away from the observer. Additionally, the reduced mobility of fast-growing broilers might mean they allow the observer to approach closer which could be misinterpreted as reduced fear.

In the same study, the so-called medium-growing broilers had shorter latencies to contact a novel object than the fast-growing broilers; however, the outcome of the tests for the medium-growing flocks were influenced by test location in the house (Averós et al., 2022). Also using the novel object test, Rasmussen et al. (2024) found the outcome to be similar between organic (Ranger Gold) and conventional (Ross 308) broilers assessed near the end of production.

Overall, it is difficult to discern a clear relationship between fear and growth rate in broilers since responses seem to depend on the type of test and the environment it is conducted in.

Overview of recording methods

Two commonly used tests of fear response are the avoidance distance test and the novel object test.

The avoidance distance test is described in the broiler WelfareQuality® protocol as an observer approaching a group of at least 3 birds, squatting for 10 seconds, and then counting the number of birds within 1 meter of the observer (proxy for arm's length). This process is repeated 21 times at different locations around the barn. This test assumes that more birds closer to the observer is indicative of less fear of humans and consequently better welfare.

The novel object test is conducted by presenting the birds with an unknown object (e.g., multicoloured baton) and observing their reaction at different locations within the barn. At each location, the observer waits several minutes then counts the number of animals within a bird-length radius from the novel object. These tests can also include assessing the latency (time) to approach or contact the novel object (Averós et al., 2022). This test assumes that the more birds within a bird-length of the object, or the quicker they interact with the object, the less fearful they are. This test is included in the laying hen WelfareQuality® protocol, but is not currently included in the broiler chicken protocol, although it is still regularly used in broiler studies (WelfareQuality®, 2009).

Suitability for welfare assessment

Fear tests are not currently recommended ABIs for assessing welfare specifically related to growth rate. Evidence linking growth rate to fear response is inconsistent and the interpretation of the test outcomes can be affected by stocking density, housing conditions, as well as other factors like early life experiences and social stress. Moreover, impaired walking ability in fast-growing broilers may directly limit their capacity to approach or avoid stimuli, which may cause bias and misinterpretation of test results. Therefore, although this ABI can be useful in other welfare assessment contexts, fear response ABIs may not be informative for specifically assessing the welfare impact of growth rate.

4 Conclusions

Growth rate can have implications for broiler chicken welfare, with the strongest and most consistent effects supported by the scientific literature being observed for walking ability and related mobility outcomes. These ABIs should therefore be prioritised for assessing growth related welfare impacts, along with complementary ABIs such as footpad dermatitis, leg straightness, and cleanliness for additional context. Additional ABIs like plumage and skin condition, positive behaviour, and QBA can enrich welfare assessments, but their interpretation is more context dependent and less specific to growth rate alone based on the available scientific evidence.

5 Recommendations for Welfare Assessment

This guidance is not intended to provide a comprehensive list of all ABIs relevant to broiler welfare assessment. Instead, emphasis has been placed on ABIs that are supported by sufficient scientific evidence demonstrating differences between broiler breeds with different growth rates. In addition, recommended ABIs were selected based on their feasibility for routine on-farm inspections, prioritising measures that do not require specialized equipment or extensive post-mortem examination. It should also be acknowledged that although the presented ABIs have been reported to differ between broiler populations with different growth rates, there are considerable interactions between the environment and the genetic potential for growth (EFSA, 2010).

Recommended ABIs are summarised in Table 1. Walking ability appears to be the strongest and most robust ABI for assessing welfare consequences related to broiler growth rate. Evidence linking increasing growth rate to impaired walking ability is consistent across breeds, production systems, and experimental manipulations, and impaired gait is directly associated with pain, reduced functional capacity, and restricted expression of motivated behaviours. Footpad dermatitis and other indicators related to prolonged litter contact provide valuable complementary information, particularly where reduced mobility leads to increased sitting behaviour, although these measures are more strongly influenced by stocking density, management and environmental conditions. Activity-based indicators, including simple measures such as standing versus lying or automated activity indices computed using video data, can further support assessment of growth-rate-related welfare impacts when interpreted alongside gait measures. In contrast, indicators such as fear response, qualitative behavioural assessment, and integument measures (e.g. cleanliness, feather cover, and injuries) currently show weaker or more context-dependent associations with growth rate and should be considered supplementary rather than primary ABIs.

For ABIs based on visual scoring systems and assessed by multiple observers (e.g., walking ability using the Bristol scale, cleanliness, footpad dermatitis), it is important to ensure there is sufficient inter-observer reliability. Observer consistency can be improved through joint scoring training exercises in which multiple observers assess the same birds and compare results until an acceptable level of agreement is reached (e.g., $\geq 80\%$ agreement). Regular calibration and refresher training is recommended to maintain scoring reliability over time.

When ABIs are used to compare broiler welfare related to growth rate between different flocks, assessments should be conducted at comparable body weights and under similar husbandry conditions wherever possible. Differences between breeds with different growth rates typically become more pronounced as they grow and so welfare assessments near the end of the production are the most informative. For example, the RSPCA BBWAP specifies conducting assessments at 2.2 kg live weight. Differences in stocking density, management practices, or housing conditions can influence ABIs and should be accounted for if the goal is to determine the effect of growth rate.

Table 1. Summary of recommended ABIs to assess broiler chicken welfare relative to growth rate.

ABI	Strengths	Limitations	Example reference for recording method
Walking ability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong & consistent relationship with growth rate Reflects health and ability to perform behaviours Option for objective recording through latency-to-lie test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires trained observers if using gait scoring method 	<p>Gait scoring (RSPCA, 2017; WelfareQuality®, 2009)</p> <p>Latency-to-lie test (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2024; Riber et al., 2024)</p>
Activity level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong & consistent relationship with growth rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently routinely feasible on farm 	Not currently included in assessment protocols.
Immobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong & consistent relationship with growth rate Feasible for on-farm assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not distinguish between physical ability and behavioural motivation 	(Marchewka et al., 2015; Marchewka et al., 2013).
Mortality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Routinely recorded Broad indicator of significant welfare compromise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Too late for intervention on current flock Influenced by housing and management 	(RSPCA, 2017; WelfareQuality®, 2009)
Leg straightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflects developmental effects of growth rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires trained observers 	(RSPCA, 2017)
Footpad dermatitis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feasible and widely used Evidence for pain from footpad dermatitis in poultry Relatively consistent relationship with growth rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Influenced by housing, management, and season Footpad lesions can be challenging to see on farm if covered by dirt or litter 	(EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2022a; RSPCA, 2017; WelfareQuality®, 2009)
Hock burn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feasible and widely used Indicates prolonged litter contact associated with reduced mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Influenced by housing, management, and season 	(RSPCA, 2017; WelfareQuality®, 2009)
Positive & preferred behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Captures aspects of positive welfare associated with the ability and motivation to express high-energy behaviours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Influenced by observation conditions Some conflicting results for growth rate effect 	(Marchewka et al., 2015; Marchewka et al., 2013)
Cleanliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feasible and widely used Indicates prolonged litter contact associated with reduced mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Influenced by housing, management, and season 	(EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2022b; RSPCA, 2017; WelfareQuality®, 2009)
QBA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Holistic assessment of flock affective state influenced by activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subjective Observer effect on outcome 	(WelfareQuality®, 2009)

	level and behavioural expression
Skin lesions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasible and widely used • Indicates skin damage from pecks or scratches, typically targeting birds with reduced mobility • Influenced by activity level (WelfareQuality®, 2009) – more active birds / more complex environments may result in more scratches • Influenced by stocking density, management, and housing

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About EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is one of the four European Union Reference Centres for Animal Welfare. It focuses on poultry and other small farmed animals welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from hatch/birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's main objective is to scientifically and technically support the European Commission and Member States for implementation of welfare legislation. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens;
- Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

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EURCAW-Poultry-SFA receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following four partner institutions:

- ANSES, France
- IRTA, Spain
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Activities of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Good Practices
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics, identify research needs and perform scientific and technical studies to fill the gaps of knowledge;
- Training
Reviewing existing training activities and developing new training materials, webinars and knowledge pills for official inspectors and competent authorities;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, and newsletter.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of poultry and other small farmed animals' welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of poultry and other small farmed animals welfare in the EU. For more information go to the Q2E webform available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw>. All Q2E answers are available [online](#).